

OPINION

Sustainable society or mass extinction, that is the question

Dragan S Hajdukovic^a, Ivan Hajdukovic^b, Anja Milica Hajdukovic^a

^aINFI, Cetinje, Montenegro

^bEuro-Mediterranean Economists Association (EMEA), Barcelona, Spain

Summary

Our “civilization” is organized in a non-sustainable manner. *A very fast transition to a sustainable society is the most important task in the history of humankind.* As an invitation for a scientific (but also public) reflection and action, we present (in our opinion) the most fundamental shortcomings of our destructive “civilization”, together with the potential, sometimes radical (but necessary) reforms.

First, in order to give transition a chance, we should declare a planetary state of emergency, agreed by the United Nations within the next 3 years.

Second, the knowledge must be the principal cornerstone of a sustainable society and scientists must have the power to prevent activities that menace survival of humankind and life on Earth. Consequently, we suggest adding a fourth power, “the power of knowledge” (or “scientific power”), to the already existing powers: Executive, Legislative and Judicial. In face of a mass extinction, for the first time in history, scientists have an unavoidable responsibility to ask for such a new global system of decision making.

Third, in a sustainable society, we must have *production for the quality of life* of all people on Earth, which (at least within the current economic system) may be incompatible with the present paradigm of production for profit.

Of course, all this seem like a utopia, and presumably it is, yet this is the first time in human history that our survival depends on our ability to realise such utopias.

Pollution and climate perturbation – our way to collective suicide

We witness a terrifying pollution of water, soil and air with alarming impact on biosphere and in particular on our food quality and human health. One good example is phytoplankton; producer of about one half of oxygen we breathe and the base of virtually every ocean food web. Without phytoplankton Ocean would be a biological (and also economic) desert. Microplastics within the phytoplankton is a fact of life (1, 2), with a negative impact on phytoplankton photosynthesis, reproduction and growth; in the worst case, if we don't slow down our war with Nature, the extinction of phytoplankton, may become a reality.

In addition to pollution, as a result of our perturbation of climate (3, 4, 5), in the best case, large parts of the Earth will become hostile to life, together with a relatively small (perhaps of the order of 10%) extinction of species (6, 7). In the worst case the result of pollution and climate perturbation will be an uninhabitable planet with a mass extinction of plants and animals including humankind.

The fact that we are on the brink of self-extinction (8, 9) shows that human society on Earth is organised in a non-sustainable manner. *The most important and the most urgent task of humankind*

is a fast transition from the current non-sustainable society to a society organized in a sustainable way, with a new economic model consistent with the planet's biocapacity.

On the way to a sustainable society, we must perform a series of urgent reforms; in our opinion the most fundamental ones are described below.

We must declare a planetary state of emergency

Transition to a society organized in a sustainable way, must take a few decades but we must be aware that we are just about to cross a number of tipping points and very close to the "Point of No Return". In order to give transition a chance, we should declare a planetary state of emergency, agreed by the United Nations within the next 3 years. A planetary state of emergency is both a necessary and very unlikely step; we permanently do much less than necessary to prevent a mass extinction that includes humankind.

Of course, in order to minimize the inevitable perturbations in economy, a planetary state of emergency must be carefully defined and prepared within UN, by a multidisciplinary team of outstanding scientists. Unfortunately, we must choose between a controllable perturbation of economy and a dramatic and irreversible climate perturbation.

Let us give a few examples (with provisional numbers) of very different measures that may be included in the state of emergency. The use of passenger's cars (i.e., the essence available for passenger's cars) has to be reduced to 1/2 of the present day use. Cities must assure public transport free of charge. Infrastructure deployment and mobility planning must be based on sustainability to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and facilitate the transition. Companies must give at least 50% longer guarantee for their products compared with the actual guarantees; a new product cannot be considered ready for production and cannot be produced if guarantee of minimum 5 years is not given. The multidisciplinary team of scientists must have right to give veto (or impose moratorium) to especially damaging projects...

Of course, United Nations has different scientific bodies; for instance, "The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change" (IPCC). The IPCC prepares comprehensive Assessment Reports about knowledge on climate change, its causes, potential impacts and response options. The full version of the current Sixth Assessment Report (3, 4, 5) has about 8000 pages, simplified and reduced to about 120 pages for policymakers; however, you can bet that only a tiny minority of presidents, prime ministers and ministers of UN countries and a tiny minority of the richest people in the world have read the simplified reports. A fact of life is that until now, scientists and knowledge were in the service of different centres of power or, at best, have been badly heard advisers.

Production for the quality of life of all people versus production for profit

In our "civilisation" the main (if not the only) purpose of production is profit (hence, we may call it *production for profit*) what is apparently *incompatible* with the natural goal of production which is the quality of life of all people on Earth (hence, we may call it *production for the quality of life*).

The simplest example of fundamental differences between these two kinds of production is the quality of products; the highest possible quality and lifespan of products is interest of people, but (at least within the current economic system) a menace to profit of producers. Imagine cars, laptops, washing machines and many other products with (what is technologically quite possible) a few times longer lifespan and hence a large decrease in amount of production; what a dream for customers and what a nightmare for producers. That is why we have a worldwide phenomenon; many products are

intentionally produced with much lower quality and lifespan than possible from the technological point of view.

The above example shows that in many cases, the same quality of life can be achieved with a significant decrease of production; the quantity of *production for profit* is never smaller but it is often much larger than the corresponding quantity of *production for the quality of life*. The growth in quality and lifespan of products, leads to a degrowth in the quantity of production (and hence to a decrease of pollution and the use of energy and resources). Consequently, a sustainable society must not tolerate the production of products that are of the lower quality and lifespan than possible technologically. The open question is if and how the production for profit and the production for the quality of life can be reconciled.

Of course, it cannot be claimed without the appropriate scientific studies but apparently, production for the quality of life is inevitable cornerstone of a sustainable organized society.

Note that all this is different and shouldn't be confused with the already existing and respectable political and economic theory called degrowth.

Organization of society based on the scientific knowledge versus organisation based on the power of mighty groups to impose and maintain their interests

In our "civilisation" the scientific knowledge is considered only as a tool for assuring a more profitable production. However, virtually in all other cases, the scientific knowledge is neglected and scientists are kept in a powerless position by the present democratic system of decision making. It is a system based on the separation of executive, legislative and judicial power, which are apparently, to an unknown (but significant) extent, influenced by non-formal centres of power.

In simple words you are forbidden to fly a human made aircraft without the appropriate knowledge recognized by a pilot licence. However, you don't need any knowledge or licence to fly the largest aircraft that we have; a planet with 8 billion people. Not only that you are allowed to fly the largest aircraft but you can do it throwing out of the plane all pilots. What a sustainable flight.

Knowledge must be the principal cornerstone of a sustainable society; consequently, scientists must be in the service of humankind and not servants of any centre of power. We must think about the best way to give to scientists a sufficient power to prevent activities that menace survival of humankind and life on Earth. We must stay open to all ideas including the idea to add a fourth power, the power of knowledge, to the already existing executive, legislative and judicial power.

During the long history, human society was organised in different ways. All political and economic systems (from slave society and feudalism to socialism and capitalism) were a result of power of mighty groups to impose and maintain their interests. Human society was never organised on the basis of the scientific reflection and knowledge, but now, in the time of our greedy and mindless war with Nature, the achievement of such an organisation is both absolutely urgent and necessary for our survival. In plain words, the fourth power, the power of knowledge, must assure the respect of laws of Nature, in some analogy with the judicial power that assures the respect of human laws.

Other reforms

So far, we were focussed on what is (in our opinion) crucial to prevent the mass extinction; however, we must be aware and take seriously many other obstacles on the way to a sustainable society and a lovely home to all people. Let us give just a few lines of a long list.

Human mind is polluted (not less than water, soil and air) with consumer mentality, different prejudices and intolerances...

There is an extreme concentration of power in hands of a small number of people and states. For instance, can we have a sustainable society if a few hundred richest people in the world have more than poorest half of humankind?

An unsuccessful general education and a very low level of general knowledge is a worldwide problem. In our system of production for profit, the ideal citizen is a working machine; a knowledgeable citizen is not priority. By the way, the fact that only a tiny minority of people has a good general knowledge is the cornerstone of our destructive attitude towards life-supporting systems on Earth.

Last but not least there is the pressing problem of the population growth.

Outlook

Already 32 years have passed from the first (1990) to the current Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Despite the excellent work of IPCC scientists, this was a period of the alarming increase of the environmental pollution and the level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. According to AR6, situation now is much worse than 3 decades ago. We are on the way to pass the 1.5^oC threshold by 2040 and in the worst scenario we may end with a virtually uninhabitable planet at the end of this century.

Imagine a police officer preventing doctors to help people who were seriously injured in a car accident. Of course, it is impossible in the case of a car accident, but it is just happening in the case of our dying planet; scientists are prevented to help. If the “power of knowledge” (or scientific power) existed as a fourth power the last 3 decades, the world today was not going to be (as warned by the UN Secretary General, António Guterres) on a “fast track” to disaster (10), facing a “collective suicide”(11).

In face of a likely mass extinction, for the first time in human history, scientists have an unavoidable responsibility to ask and win the right to be one of the four separate powers (legislative, executive, judicial and scientific power) within a new global system of decision making. Scientists involved in IPCC, scientists from different Universities and research centres, scientists from emerging organisations as for instance The Alliance of World Scientists (12) and Scientists Warning Foundation (13)...; everyone must raise the voice and ask the right to have a society based on the knowledge. If the rebellion of the scientists awakens the hope and support of the citizens, we still can save life on Earth. But this crucial reform of our society, together with a planetary state of emergency, must be accomplished before the end of the third decade of the 21st century.

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